

Integrating Forensic Accounting with Conventional Financial Accounting : A Forward-Looking Approach

RAJANI GUPTA AND ARVIND KUMAR

Abstract : *Forensic accounting is a comparatively innovative field of career that has prolonged rapidly since its inception. The need for it is growing every day. Forensic accountants are extremely endowed individuals who possess meticulous knowledge in several areas such as general accounting principles, criminal behavior, the law, frauds and computerized systems. Due to increasing scenario of frauds in India, it is evident that now a day's criminals are becoming technology-savvy and developing new methods to perpetuate crimes. Hence, in the era of digitization, the necessity of forensic accounting is growing for their "niche" accounting, auditing, lawful and analytical skills. Therefore, the introduction of forensic accounting as a new area of accounting has been thrown in the "forefront of the crusade" against financial dishonesty and accounting scandals.*

Since the start of the twenty-first century, several financial and online frauds occur that led to the downfall of many enterprises. To meet these kinds of scandals, there is drastic increase in the demand of forensic accounting for which the Committee on Information Technology (CIT) of the Since forensic audit, fraud detection, and prevention have been recognized by the Institute of Chartered Accountants (ICAI) as specialty areas, the ICAI has begun offering certificate programs in these areas. The present study aims at analyzing the futuristic approach towards integration of forensic accounting with conventional financial accounting in India. The researcher tried an attempt to describe the perceived benefits as well as obstacles regarding integration of forensic accounting with conventional accounting according to gathered information from 100 responders including student group, academicians and professionals.

Keywords : Forensic Accounting, Accounting Frauds, Financial Accounting, Accounting Curriculum, Accounting Professionals etc.

Dr.Rajani Gupta, Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, DDU Government Degree College, Sahjanwa, Gorakhpur.

Prof.Arvind Kumar, Senior Most Professor, Former Head & Dean, Faculty of Commerce, University of Lucknow, Lucknow.

Introduction

“True and Fair” view of financial state of affairs regarding financial statements must be depicted as per the fundamental objective of GAAP. But due to great financial frauds, there is a strong need for detailed investigation of irregularities in the segment of financial reporting. Forensic accounting as a new scope of accounting came into limelight due to white collar crimes, cyber crimes, financial frauds and the rising complexity of corporate environment. According to Arokiasamy & Cristal (2009), forensic accounting can be described as the application of financial skills and investigative mentality to unsettled issues, conducted within the context of rules of evidence. Adegbie and Fakile (2012) said that the Forensic accounting is generally described as the new scope of accounting which incorporates accounting and auditing skills with investigating techniques and professional skepticism. Forensic accounting is the practice of utilizing accounting, auditing and investigation skill to assist in legal matter and the application of specialized body of knowledge to the evidence of economic transaction and reporting suitable in the purpose of establishing accountability or valuation of administrative proceedings. .

The application of accounting principles and methods to legal issues is known as forensic accounting. When fraud, bribery, or embezzlement is proven, it requires reporting; the report is then used as evidence in administrative or legal actions. (Dhar and Sarkar, 2010). With the overview of integrating forensic accounting with regular accounting, The Treadway Commission (1987) recommended that accounting curricula provide greater consideration towards investigating the frauds in financial sector for which they suggested that the existing curriculum is lacking in this crucial area. Perhaps forensic accounting ought to take center stage in accounting curricula because of the wide range of expertise needed for forensic accounting to handle litigation support, provide expert evidence, and carry out fraud investigations.

Historical March of Forensic Accounting in India

The term “Forensic accountant” was coined for the very first time in 1946 by Maurica E. peloubet in his essay “Forensic Accounting: Its Place in Today’s Economy.” Archaeological findings reveled that during 3300-3500 BC, accountants in Egypt were involved in the activity of prevention and detection of fraud. During 18th century, there was a tight bond formed between accountancy and legal profession. Many amendments made in financial statement disclosure can be attributed to frauds occur in corporate sector. In 1930s, Frank Wilson was credited for the birth of forensic accounting when he

was working as a CPA for the US Internal Revenue Service. At that time, Wilson was tasked with looking into the transactions of the gangster Al Capone who was involved in illegal activities including violent crimes. In this case, Capone found guilty of tax evasion for which he got punishment of 10 years in Federal Prison. Hence, Wilson is considered as America's first high profile forensic accountant. After this case, the importance of accounting for crimes is increasing. In Indian context, the history of investigative accounting is related with ancient times of Mauryan. In Indian history, the renowned forty forms of misappropriation were first addressed by Kautilya in his book "Kautilya Arthashastra." Since the commencement of 21st century, many financial and virtual frauds occur that led to the downfall or collapse of many enterprises. To meet these kinds of scandals, there is drastic increase in the demand of forensic accounting for which the Committee on Information Technology (CIT) of the Institute of Chartered Accountant (ICAI) has identified forensic audit, fraud detection and prevention as one of the niche area and has started to conduct forensic accounting and fraud detection certificate program. Hence, in present era, when it comes to identifying and preventing financial crime, chartered accountants have the monopoly because of the nature of skill required to examine such frauds.

Significance of Forensic Accounting in India

Within the accounting industry, forensic accounting is a rapidly expanding field and has added new dimensions to accounting education and practices (Razae et.al, 1992). Today many stakeholders expect from accountants to play a crucial part in providing reasonable assurance towards appropriate corporate governance, trustworthy financial reporting and checking financial fraudulent activities. Due to increase in demand for fraud investigation, the necessity and significance of professional forensic accounting was highlighted by a number of significant initiatives, including the Treadway Commission (1987), the Sponsoring Organization Committee's 1992 report, and the new Proposed Statement on Auditing Standards (SAS).

Beckoff and Schrader (2000) hypothesized in their paper that "adding forensic accounting course to the accounting curriculum can greatly benefit the three major stakeholders in accounting- academic institutions, students and the employers of accounting graduates." Although there is increasing the demand for forensic accountants, courses being offered at the level of university around the world have not reserved velocity with this demand.

Literature Review

Extensive study has been conducted in the field of forensic accounting worldwide. Nonetheless, academics' interest in this field is just beginning to grow in developing nations like India. The following are a few prominent forensic accounting studies:

Al-Tarawneh, M., & Haloush, H. A. (2023) in their study report entitled “The role of forensic accountants in online dispute resolution: Benefits and challenges” identified the theoretical and conceptual frameworks supporting the use of forensic accountants in online dispute resolution through a thorough literature review and expert interviews. It has also emphasized the significance of having a well-trained team of forensic accountants and a strong technological framework to ensure the smooth operation of the ODR process.

Shbeilat M.K. & Alqatamin R.M. (2022) in their research paper entitled “Challenges and Forward-looking Roles of Forensic Accounting in Combating Money laundering : Evidence from the Developing Market” suggests that to enhance the efficacy of forensic accountants (represented by the JACPA) as expert witnesses in the investigation of white-collar crimes and money laundering, this study helps to highlight the significance of coordination between forensic accountants and the judicial authorities (ACFE, n.d.). By bridging the knowledge gap regarding the function of forensic accounting techniques in combating money laundering and illuminating the primary challenges faced by forensic accountants, which demand collaboration between the JACPA and regulators, the study also adds to the body of literature.

Dr. Chaya R (2021) in her research paper entitled “An empirical study on the impact of Forensic Accounting in Corporate Sector and its exponential Growth” determined The practicality of forensic accounting as a means of minimizing corporate fraud, assessed its suitability for an efficient internal control system, and recommended the practice for producing high-quality financial reports and a practical way to reduce the number of fraud-related incidents.

Supriya. H (2019) in her research article “Forensic Accounting – Emerging Trend in Indian Accounting Field” described that a new development in the Indian accounting industry is forensic accounting. It is different from other accountant, as other accountant look at the number but forensic accounting look beyond the number. It involves integration of investigation, accounting and auditing abilities to continue with a legal situation. Forensic accounting came into limelight in India after corporate frauds and white collar crimes; however there is difficulty

in adopting it. In summary, the writer states that forensic accounting should not become the subject of a selected few specialized area. It ought to be included in undergraduate and post graduate curriculum across the country. This initiative will help both the corporate as well as government sector to initially maintain an eye on crime.

Kramer, B., Seda, M. and Bobashev, G. (2017), in their research paper “Current opinions on forensic accounting education”, tried to ascertain the views of educators and practitioners regarding forensic accounting education. After analyzing data, they came to the conclusion that while both groups agreed that there will be a greater need for forensic accounting in the near future; they preferred that graduate and undergraduate students have access to a different course or degree. The investigation discovered that there are a number of noteworthy variations between the educators and practitioners opinion regarding forensic accounting content and preferred teaching techniques. Practitioners are with the opinion to consider topics which are exterior to traditional accounting as more important topics to include in forensic accounting education and should consider high value teaching techniques that add an experiential learning component.

Sorunke, Olukayode Abayomi (2016) in their research paper “Integrating Forensic Accounting into the Accounting Curriculum in Nigerian Universities: Challenges and Remedies” stated that the accounting profession has been witnessed to a rising demand for professional trained in forensic accounting. But their research showed that no Nigerian university is offering forensic accounting either as individual course and/or entire fraud accounting programme. Their study investigated the challenges militating against Nigerian university in their quest to integrate forensic accounting into accounting curriculum as been done in other parts of the world.

Basu S. (2014) in his research paper entitled “Forensic Accounting in the Cyber World: A New Challenge for Accountants” stated that today data storage has shifted from individual PCs to servers or multiple servers to cloud storage that make the job of forensic accountant, auditors and investigators much complex. Now days, the traditional accounting has failed in order to deal with the emerging complexity of management requirements. Further, it is not much capable in checking or controlling frauds in India. Irregularities related with corporate sector starting from Mundra case to the Satyam case has exposed that the traditional accounting system is unable to keep pace with the prospering and changing business scenario. To prevent economic frauds and to preserve national

wealth, the American Law and British Bribery Act has demanded for a new approach. Fraud irregularities and compliance lapses have necessitated the growing importance of Forensic Accounting.

The author continued on to state that forensic accounting has emerged as a useful instrument for stopping white collar crime. It is still in its infancy and needs ongoing technological support as well as international collaboration. It will grow into a specialist field of accountancy, and regulators and law enforcement will value it more and more every day.

Hidayat & Ali Al-Sadiq (2014) concluded in their research "A Survey on the Need to offer Forensic Accounting Education in the Kingdom of Bahrain" that there will be a rise in Bahrain's need for forensic accounting education. in near future. The majority of respondents to their survey believe that forensic accounting courses ought to be included in Bahraini universities' accounting curricula. In order to preserve a balance between the supply and demand for forensic accountants, they proposed in their study that institutions in Bahrain offer at least one forensic accounting course, mostly for senior students.

Research Gap

Numerous studies have been conducted on the topic of forensic accounting across the world. But in developing countries like India, very few studies have been done. The researchers have emphasized on the theoretical and conceptual framework of forensic accounting. The industrial revolution has resulted in a number of financial scandals and scams, which has raised the need for forensic accounting in India. Keeping this point of view, an attempt is made to analyze the relevance and method of integrating forensic accounting with conventional financial accounting in India.

Objectives of Study

1. To analyze the demand of integrating forensic accounting with conventional financial accounting in India.
2. To compare and contrast the views of students, academicians and professionals on the futuristic approach towards the methods of integrating forensic accounting with conventional financial accounting.
3. To examine the perceived benefits and obstacles regarding integration of forensic accounting with conventional financial accounting.

Hypothesis of the Study

1. H₀ : Nothing noticeably different exists between the level of conventional accounting education and demand for forensic accounting in India.
2. H₀ : There is no significant difference between the view point of students, academicians and professionals regarding integration method of forensic accounting with conventional financial accounting.

Research Methodology

Universe : The population regarding this research study consists of all accounting profession practitioners, academicians related with accounting stream, researchers and prospective users among students of forensic accounting.

Sample Size : A sample size of 100 respondents has been gathered for this research investigation. which includes responses of accounting academicians, practicing accountants, executive members and students who are potential users of forensic accounting.

Data Collection Method : This study relies on data collected via questionnaire (Google form) as primary source of data collection. The questionnaire's inquiries are broken down into two parts. The first section of questionnaire collects demographic profile of respondents while the Second section of questionnaire collects information about respondent's perception and their familiarity with forensic accounting and their opinion about the futuristic approach regarding integration of forensic accounting with conventional financial accounting. For this investigation, a convenient sampling strategy was employed.

Statistical tool for data analysis : To evaluate the data collected from questionnaire, SPSS software has been used to compute descriptive statistics for frequencies and percentage and to test the hypothesis, chi-square (χ^2) test has been used. Some charts and tables have been used to support this study.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Demographic Profile of Respondents

In first section of questionnaire, the demographic profile of respondents were asked which is depicted in the following chart -

Chart-1 :

Source : Primary data collection.

The above chart 1 indicates the demographic profile of 100 respondents. Out of total respondents, 61% are male and 39% are female. In terms of age group, 23% respondents fall under the age group of 18-25, 53% are related with the age group of 26-35, 13% respondents come under the age group of 36-45 and 11% respondents are from the age group of 46-55. In terms of qualification of respondents, 6% are graduate, 35% are post graduate, 15% respondents have professional degree like CA, CMA, and CS etc. while 44% respondents are doctorate of philosophy.

Testing of Hypothesis

H0 : 1. Nothing noticeably different exists between the level of conventional accounting education and demand for forensic accounting in India.

Table-1 : Cross Tabulation Regarding Demand for Forensic Accounting and Qualification of Respondents

In India, white-collar crimes are rising. Corporate India has suffered a loss of financial resources and prestige as a result of this. As a result, hiring forensic accountants has become essential to stopping and dealing with financial crimes and fraud.	Qualification of respondents				Total
	Graduation	Post Graduation	Professional Degree (CA, CMA, CS etc.)	Ph.D.	
Strongly Agree	4	20	4	21	49
Agree	2	11	11	22	46
Neutral	0	2	0	0	2
Disagree	0	2	0	1	3
Total	6	35	15	44	100

Source : Primary data collection.

Based on the above table, it can be seen that 49% of respondents strongly agree and 46% agree that forensic accounting is the best way to investigate white-collar crimes in India.

Table-2 : Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	12.093 ^a	9	.208
Likelihood Ratio	13.122	9	.157
Linear-by-Linear Association	.065	1	.798
N of Valid Cases	100		

a. 10 cells (62.5%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

In the above table, the value of chi-square statistic is 12.093 and the p-value appears in the same row in the asymptotic Significance column is 0.208 i.e., greater than the designated alpha value 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted that nothing noticeably different exists between the level of education and demand for forensic accounting in India. At every level of qualification, respondents are agreeing that the services of forensic accounting have become necessary to prevent and resolve the financial crimes in India.

1. **H₀** : There is no significant difference between the view point of students, academicians and professionals regarding integration method of forensic accounting with conventional financial accounting.

Table-3 : Method of Integrating Forensic Accounting with Conventional Accounting as per Occupation of Respondents

Occupation	Forensic Accounting would best be incorporated into the accounting curriculum by-			Total
	Offering a separate forensic accounting courses	Integrating forensic accounting into current accounting system	Should not be integrated at all	
Student	3	22	2	27
Academician	19	32	1	52
Professional	1	14	0	15
Accountants	1	5	0	6
Executives				
Total	24	73	3	100

Source : Primary data computed through SPSS.

The opinions of respondents from a variety of professions about how to incorporate forensic accounting into traditional financial accounting curricula are shown in the above table. According to the data, 24% of respondents believe that students ought to have access to a distinct forensic accounting course. While 3% of respondents thought that forensic accounting should not be merged with financial accounting at all, 73% of respondents felt it would be preferable to integrate forensic accounting into the current accounting system. The majority of respondents support incorporating forensic accounting into the present accounting system, the study says.

Table-4 : Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	12.006 ^a	6	.062
Likelihood Ratio	12.895	6	.045
Linear-by-Linear Association	.266	1	.606
N of Valid Cases	100		

a. 7 cells (58.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .18.

In above table, the value of Pearson Chi-square test statistic is 12.006. The corresponding p-value of the test statistic is 0.062. Since, the p-value is greater than the significance level i.e., 0.05, we do not reject the null hypothesis. Rather we conclude that there is no significant difference between the methods of integrating forensic accounting with traditional accounting as per the occupation of respondents. In other words, there is no association between the occupation of respondents and opinion regarding integrating forensic accounting with traditional accounting.

Perceived Benefits of Forensic Accounting

Forensic accounting has emerged as a famous and extensively demanded area of accounting. According to Aldridge, Corporations have three goals after discovering a fraud has been committed: "first, to identify the fraudster, secondly to secure the evidence to legally terminate their contract, and thirdly to make sure it cannot happen again." Forensic accountants were educated in every of these areas. They can become aware of and discover fraud and are educated to accumulate applicable proof. Forensic accountants are able to supply helpful hints for future fraud prevention. Their talents are unique and incredibly essential in the financial world. Respondents were asked about the perceived benefits of forensic accounting education. These benefits are -

Chart-2 : Benefits of Forensic Accounting Education

Source : Primary data collection.

The perceived advantages of forensic accounting education in India are shown in the above chart. The participants were requested to select multiple benefits through pre-structured questionnaire. The majority of respondents i.e., 84% think that the financial reporting's credibility will be enhanced via forensic accounting. followed by the view of 76% respondents that it will promote responsible corporate governance. 68% respondents think that it will improve brand reputation and authority, 63% are agree that the knowledge and skill of forensic accounting will make students more desirable at the market place. 61% respondents have the opinion that it will minimize losses and improve efficiency of organization.

Perceived Obstacles of Forensic Accounting

Respondents were asked regarding specific factors that may be obstacles in providing forensic accounting education in India. These responses are summarized in the following chart-

Chart-3 : Obstacles of Forensic Accounting Education

Source : Primary data collection.

The above chart describes the obstacles regarding implementation of forensic accounting education in India. 75% respondents think that there is lack of flexibility in curricular contents. 72% respondents believe that there is lack of instructional materials to proper implement the forensic accounting in India. 68% respondents feel that there would be lack of financial resources or support to implement this course in curriculum. 65% respondents reflect that there would be lack of interest among students to learn a new field of education who are not desirable to go in the field of accounting as their career. They have fear of over burden. 58% respondents think that there is lack of well qualified faculty to teach forensic accounting efficiently.

Conclusion and Suggestions

Due to growth in business sector and advancement of technology, there is a strong need of forensic accounting to control over the financial reporting. Now the people are becoming increasingly conscious of the financial misappropriation and frauds being occur in corporate sector and have fear of potential risk in investing these sectors. In India, people should be made aware about the Forensic Accounting as it is far genuinely useful in investigating financial frauds.

Based on the perceived benefits of forensic accounting education in India, many opportunities are there to the forensic accounting stakeholders such as students, academicians, practitioners and the customers. If we emphasize on students, they would be able to boost their knowledge and skill in the field of accounting by mixing up their acquaintance regarding accounting with the holistic knowledge about the forensic accounting. Hence, it needs to be made part of curriculum in undergraduate as well as in post graduate level. Universities who offer accounting course at their post graduate level should encourage specialization in forensic accounting among its students. Requisite amendments within the law ought to be undertaken to establish the importance of forensic accounting in India.

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